

PESTLE ANALYSIS OF COOPERATIVE BANKS- A CASE STUDY

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: The study focus is to understand the analyze the cooperative banks' financial results and offerings.

Design: Secondary data is compiled from previously published articles, books, and websites like research gate, bank websites, and google scholar. PESTLE analysis is also used to analyse the bank.

Findings: Using PESTLE analysis, the study looks into the fundamentals and significance of cooperative banks. The study's findings enable it to offer recommendations for steady outcomes of a firm's policies and operations.

Originality: The study emphasizes the prospects of cooperative banks and provides principles for collaboration, peer support, democratic decision-making, and assisting all segments of the community.

Paper Type: Case Study.

Keywords: Cooperative Bank, Banking, Financial, Government, Organisation Structure, Products And Services, PESTLE Analysis.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cooperative banks provide services to private citizens and small businesses. Services include the exchange of various items, such as deposits, financial assistance and guidance, including loans, savings accounts, certificates of deposit, and business banking accounts. All facets of human existence have been impacted by new technologies, and finance is no exception. Financial technology has likely been the most often used word in the financial industry over the past ten years [1]. Due to a lack of data, research on governance in cooperative banks is scarce [2]. Since they work with rural, semi-urban, and metropolitan communities directly, cooperative banks assist in obtaining financial support from the government, primarily in the form of short and medium-term lending. A key component of financial risk management, financial performances refer based on how well financial goals have been accomplished. Calculating the monetary value of the results of a firm's policies and activities is what this procedure entails. Considering their clients are also credit union members, cooperative banks have a unique business strategy [3].

Cooperative banks, which have trustworthy connections with the neighbourhood, might be a great source of funding for these business ventures, but they are constrained by their fundamental economic uncertainty. They don't function for financial gain, but rather to raise the members' economic status [4]. As customers purchase good moods along with the goods in banking services, the preparation and social skills of the staff play a major role in customer happiness [5]. The latest financial crisis was centered around financial intermediaries [6]. By relying on retail and relationship banking-focused business models, savings banks, and particularly cooperative banks, may favour financial inclusion of marginal customers and reduce credit rationing of small borrowers [7]. The capacity to manipulate loan loss provisions is essentially due to the existence of judgmental components of provisioning, which are tied to the identification of impaired assets and to the overall estimate of anticipated future credit losses [8]. Safeguard them from the debt trap of Loan companies and cooperative banks, persons with limited resources frequently start cooperative banks [9]. With two key concepts, cooperation has a unique approach to tackling economic challenges. connection and utilization [10].

II. RELATED WORKS

Below Table 1 shows systematic literature of review is conducted from 2007 to 2022 by using the keywords "co-operative bank", "UCBs", "Banking activity" from google scholar and research gate.

Table 1: Related works on Co-operative banks

S. No	Focus	Outcome	Reference
1	As system building permits the pursuit of scale and scope economies as well as the creation of a safety net or mutual support mechanism, cooperative banks can benefit significantly from it.	This result can be attributed to the cooperative banks' lower return volatility, which more than makes up for their lower profitability and capitalization.	Hesse, H., & Čihák, M. (2007) [11].
2	Banking activity encourages the flow of money to investments and useful purposes since it seems as simple as collecting deposits from savers and then lending the same money to borrowers.	Cooperative banks are modest businesses that work together in both urban and rural locations within the cooperative sector.	Gupta, J., & Jain, S. (2012) [12].
3	Cost containment is typically a cooperative's first priority, and it frequently begins with the HR department. These cooperatives put a lot of emphasis on how to use employee performance to carry out strategy.	It is acknowledged that cooperative firms approach human management incorrectly, which has a detrimental impact on their financial success.	Ramu, N. (2008) [13].
4	Due to shared interests, members of a certain community or profession get together to form a network.	The guiding concepts of the coorganizational operative's structure are cooperation, mutual aid, democratic decision-making, and free and open membership.	Nethala, V. J., Pathan, M. F. I., & Sekhar, M. S. C. (2022) [14].
5	Protections from constant breaking forces are a difficulty for cooperative banking institutions, and combined stock banks have trouble with managed protections.	Co-employable banks are businesses formed on cooperatives that conduct typical financial transactions. Bosses' banks are set up similarly to unique banks by gathering possessions via stocks, taking in payments, and offering credit.	Haralayya, B. (2021) [15].
6	The retail banking industry primarily focuses on providing consumers with banking, financial, and value-added services.	India's banking industry is well-capitalized, having capital ratios that are higher than the world average.	Matkar, A. (2012) [16].
7	Various economic challenges have been faced by the cooperative sector. Some of the key factors that have had a detrimental impact on how these organisations function include low capital foundations, liquidity issues, inadequate governance, a delayed use of technology, and a lack of checks and balances.	The government has implemented a number of initiatives, including amending the Banking Regulation Act in 2021 to give the Reserve Bank of India more jurisdiction, to improve the governance and oversight of the cooperative banking sector.	Zaman, A. U., Zaman, M. S., & Khan, N. A. (2022) [17].
8	The cooperative sector works to	A great idea, cooperation aspires to	Babu, K. V. S.

	address economic inequality and the negative effects of income and wealth concentration, which helps to stop the exploitation of the weaker groups by the more powerful.	create a just, civilized society.	N. J. (2012) [18].
9	The cooperative bank in India's organisational structure consists of a short-term structure and a long-term structure.	The recovery of past due amounts likewise rises as the loan outstanding of cooperative banks in India develops.	Reddy, K. N., & Chandraiah, M. (2019) [19].
10	Co-operatives are businesses that are collaboratively managed and democratically controlled by organised groups of people.	Recounting how recent global events have brought corporate governance and corporate control challenges to the forefront is undoubtedly appropriate here.	Kamesam, V. (2002) [20].
11	To research the development and effectiveness of cooperative banks	High degrees of computerization should be used by the Co-operative Bank to improve branch productivity. Additionally, they must to provide modern conveniences like passbook printing, mobile banking, ATM services, online commerce, and 24-hour access to facilities for cash deposit.	Chandanshive, D. S. B (2017) [21].
12	Urban cooperative banks primarily provide financing to various types of people for home loans, small-scale businesses, industries, and self-employment.	In order to better serve the underprivileged, these banks need to expand the number of women members as well as provide opportunities for depositors and borrowers from Schedule castes and Schedule tribes.	Khan, H. F. (2014) [22].
13	To determine the issues that customers and workers are experiencing as a result of the lack of core banking.	In addition to the staff resistance, banks are having trouble implementing core banking since there is a lack of funding and management talent.	Dhirubhai, A. (2013) [23].
14	A cooperative society is an independent group of people who have come together voluntarily to pursue their common objectives in the economic, social, and cultural arenas through a jointly owned and democratically run business.	It offers agricultural financing when both the public and commercial sectors are unable to make sizable contributions.	Karthikeyan, K. (2021) [24].
15	Due to their local focus and "relationship lending" technologies, cooperative banks have a comparative edge in financing informationally opaque borrowers.	The estimation findings show that cooperative banks significantly lessen income disparity compared to their commercial counterparts.	Minetti, R., Murro, P., & Peruzzi, V. (2021) [25].

III. OBJECTIVES

- (1) To be aware of Indian cooperative banks' lending policies.
- (2) To assess and evaluate the effectiveness of Indian cooperative banks.
- (3) To research how a cooperative bank's "size" affects its effectiveness.
- (4) To make recommendations for the best ways to boost cooperative banks' productivity.
- (5) To understand the many loan types that various client groups want.
- (6) To learn how satisfied consumers are with the lending practices of the bank.

IV. METHODOLOGY

Secondary data is collected from published scholarly articles, bank website and books from google scholar and research gate. Further, the study analyzed Cooperative bank using PESTLE analysis

V. COOPERATIVE BANKS' HISTOTY

Co-operative banks were first established in India around the beginning of the 20th century, a difficult time for Indian society.

The following is a chronology of how co-operative banking developed in India:

- (1) The Cooperative Credit Societies Act, 1904, was the initial step toward establishing a cooperative society; the Cooperative Societies Act, 1912, advanced that process.
- (2) In order to build co-operative training centers, the RBI established the Central Committee for Cooperative Training in post-independence India in 1953.
- (3) 1954 could see the establishment of the Rural Credit Survey Committee to address the issue of the financial crisis in rural areas.
- (4) The banking industry was also affected by the co-operative movement, and by the 1950s, cooperative banks had started to reach out to the general population in both rural and urban areas.

VI. COOPERATIVE BANKS' OVERVIEW

A cooperative bank is a financial institution that is owned by its members, who also double as the bank's owners and clients. People with a same interest from the same local or professional community frequently found it. It was established to support the social uplift of economically underprivileged groups and to shield them from the grasp of predatory lenders who give out loans to the needy at exorbitant interest rates. The ideas of collaboration, reciprocity, a democratic system of government and open membership inform the co-operative structure's design. It adheres to the "no profit, no loss" and "one shareholder, one vote" values.

In India, cooperative banks provide financing for urban regions through the following channels:

- Self-employment
- small-scale businesses
- Industries
- Housing finance and
- Consumer finance

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- Self-employment
- Businesses
- Small-scale enterprises
- Home loans
- Consumer loans and
- Personal loans.

CHARACTERISTICS OF CO-OPERATIVE BANK:

The following are some of the primary characteristics of cooperative banks:

(1) ENTITIES OWNED BY CUSTOMERS

Cooperative bank members serve as both the bank's shareholders and clients. As a result, the cooperative bank's goal is to give its members the finest services available rather than to increase profits. In order to offer them financial services, several cooperative banks also accept non-members.

(2) DEMOCRATS ARE IN CHARGE.

Members of cooperative banks own and manage them, and they democratically choose the board of directors. No matter how many shares a member has, co-operatives adhere to the fundamental concept of "one man, one vote," which makes sure that no member has unchecked control over other members.

(3) PROFIT DISTRIBUTION

Following the transfer of a certain amount of the revenue going into the Statutory Reserve and other reserves, the members' money is then repaid with a reasonable rate of interest. The co-operative members may also receive a portion of this profit, subject in most situations to legal and regulatory restrictions.

(4) INCLUDE RURAL POPULATIONS

It is important for the unbanked rural masses' financial inclusion.

VII. FUNCTIONS OF COOPERATIVE BANKS

(1) It provides financial assistance to persons with minimal resources and protects them from creditors who overcharge for loans and other services and target on the weak. It oversees and directs associated societies.

(2) Rural financing – At relatively lower rates, it offers funding to rural industries including livestock farming, crop farming, hatching, etc.

(3) Urban financing: This type of funding is available for residential mortgages, small-scale businesses, and other things.

VIII. COOPERATIVE BANK STRUCTURE

In India, there are two types of cooperative banking structures: short-term and long-term.

Figure 1: Structure of cooperative Banks'

Source: Author

THREE LEVELS OF SHORT-TERM STRUCTURE:

- A State Cooperative Bank is the type of business that is the most advanced.
- The Central Co-operative Bank is a Middle Level Organization.
- A smart place to start is with Primary Co-operative Credit Societies.

TWO LEVELS OF LONG -TERM:

- The State Cooperative Agriculture and Rural Development Banks at the top echelon (SCARDBs).
- Primary Cooperative Agriculture and Rural Development Banks at the district- or block-level (PCARDBs).

IX. TYPES OF COOPERATIVE BANKS IN INDIA

The following five categories make up India's co-operative banking system:

Figure 2: Types of Cooperative Banks'

Source: Author

THE PRIMARY COOPERATIVE CREDIT SOCIETY

- Residents of the area, both borrowers and non-borrowers, make up the Primary Co-operative Credit Society.
- Members' savings, share capital, and loans from central co-operative banks provide the society with its finance.
- Borrowing, which has fixed but variable borrowing capacities for both the society and its members, is the main source of their operating capital.
- Members receive loans to help with the cost of buying cattle, feed, fertilizer, and medicines.

CENTRAL CO-OPERATIVE BANKS

- Individuals who only participate in minor societies.
- Individuals who are a part of both social and professional organisations.
- The bank's capital, deposits, loans, and overdrafts come from state cooperative banks and joint stocks, which also carry out all of the functions of a joint-stock bank and lend money to their member societies within the limits of those societies' borrowing ability.

STATE COOPERATIVE BANKS

- The state co-operative bank is a federation of central co-operative banks and serves as a watchdog for the state's cooperative banking system.
- It obtains funding from share capital, deposits, loans, and overdrafts from the Reserve Bank of India.
- The state co-operative banks don't directly lend money to farmers; instead, they lend to central co-operative banks and primary societies.

LAND DEVELOPMENT BANKS

- With the aim of satisfying the farmers' long-term loan needs for developmental objectives, these are arranged into three levels, namely state, central, and primary level.
- Land development banks are supervised by the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).
- Since these banks do not accept deposits from the general public, their sources of funding are the debentures that both the Central and State governments have subscribed to.

URBAN COOPERATIVE BANKS

- It refers to major co-op banks that are situated in urban and semi-urban locations.
- Previously, the reach of these banks was constrained, but it has now been greatly expanded.
- They offer small businesses and borrowers' money and services.

X. COOPERATIVE BANKING SYSTEM HAS THE FOLLOWING PROBLEMS

➤ LOW CAPITALIZATION:

Cooperative banks can only start with a capital base of Rs. 25 lakhs, which limits their capital basis and makes it challenging for them to account for some of that money as working capital. Almost all cooperative banks have found it difficult to raise working capital.

➤ POLITICAL MANIPULATION:

In order to get great benefits, such as the sanctioning of loans that are later wiped off, politicians use them to broaden their support bases and frequently succeed in electing their candidates to the board of directors.

➤ RBI MONITORING:

The RBI's regulation of cooperative banks is less stringent than it is for commercial banks. RBI only audits the books of these banks once a year.

➤ TWO CONTROLLERS:

Coordination and management issues arise because cooperative banks are subject to a dual system of control, with the RBI and their respective State governments controlling them.

➤ TECHNOLOGY PROGRESS AND EXPERT MANAGEMENT:

Cooperative banks frequently hold back on implementing cutting-edge innovations like computerized data management. Due to a lack of resources, professional management in banks is frequently lacking in terms of staff training.

➤ FINANCE DEPENDENCE:

For refinancing options, cooperative banks rely primarily on the RBI, NABARD, and the government. Instead of relying on its constituents, it depends on the government for funding.

➤ DEFAULTED LOANS:

The number of past-due loans at cooperative banks is rising yearly, which limits the ability to recycle money and, in turn, reduces the bank's ability to lend and borrow.

XI. PESTLE ANALYSIS

Political, Economic, Social, and Technological (PEST) aspects are used to analyse the market for a certain business or organisational sector [26]. used by businesses as a tool to monitor the environment in which they operate or plan to introduce a new initiative, product, service, etc. [27]. A major factor in the conversion of offshore platforms is politics [28]. PEST analysis is used to build development strategies by doing a thorough investigation of the external environment of a business or sector [29]. PESTLE analysis makes it possible to thoroughly analyze the problems that have the cost implications on the expansion of business activities or the projects that they must support. [30].

Figure 3: PESTLE Analysis of Cooperative Banks'

Source: Author

XII. FINDINGS

- Cooperative banks not only take deposits but also make loans.
- They were created with the intention of funding rural and cottage industries, as well as agriculture and related activities.
- The Indian cooperative banks' governing body is called the National Bank for Agriculture and Rural Development (NABARD).
- Cooperative banks offer loans to their customers at significantly lower interest rates because their goal is to provide excellent services to their members rather than to generate a profit.
- Cooperative banks encouraging farmers to save money, cooperative banks have promoted investment and savings
- The paid-up share capital and reserves of a Primary Credit Society shall not exceed Rs. 1 lakh. Such a society is capable of operating banks without acquiring an RBI license.

XIII. SUGGESTION

- The banks should use reducing banking techniques including online banking, credit cards, ATMs, etc.
- The banks should prepare to launch fresh initiatives aimed at luring in new clients and retaining existing ones.
- The banks should prepare for branch expansion.
- Banks need to do a better job of enhancing their customer services.

XIV. CONCLUSION

Cooperative banks, owned by their customers, operate under the concept of "one person, one vote." Cooperative banks are frequently governed by both banking and cooperative laws. Both members and non-members can use their savings and loan services, and some of them participate in the wholesale bond, money,

and even equity markets. Since many cooperative banks are listed on public stock exchanges, non-members hold a portion of their ownership. These external stakes have the potential to dilute member control, making them potentially semi-cooperative.

In comparison to credit union systems, cooperative banking systems are frequently more interconnected. Local co-operative bank branches elect their own boards of directors and run their own businesses, but the majority of strategic choices need to be approved by the head office. Even though they federate, credit unions often keep strategic decision-making at the local level while sharing back-office tasks like access to the international payments system.

XV. REFERENCES

- [1] Pu, R., Teresiene, D., Pieczulis, I., Kong, J., & Yue, X. G. (2021). The interaction between banking sector and financial technology companies: Qualitative assessment—a case of lithuania. *Risks*, 9(1), 1- 21. Google Scholar ↗
- [2] Ghosh, S., & Ansari, J. (2018). Board characteristics and financial performance: Evidence from Indian cooperative banks. *Journal of Co-operative organization and management*, 6(2), 86-93. Google Scholar ↗
- [3] Clark, E., Mare, D. S., & Radić, N. (2018). Cooperative banks: What do we know about competition and risk preferences?. *Journal of International Financial Markets, Institutions and Money*, 52(1), 90-101. Google Scholar ↗
- [4] Mirasol, M. L., & Garcia, D. R. (2020). Assessing the performance of cooperative banks in the Philippines: a data envelopment analysis. *Int J Account*, 5(28), 37-48. Google Scholar ↗
- [5] Idzik, M. (2018, September). Rating Of The Customer Service Quality At Cooperative Banks In Mystery Shopper Study. In Proceedings of the International Scientific Conference "Economic Sciences for Agribusiness and Rural Economy"1 (1), 351-357. Google Scholar ↗
- [6] Barra, C., & Zotti, R. (2019). bank performance, financial stability and market concentration: evidence from cooperative and non-cooperative banks. *Annals of Public and Cooperative Economics*, 90(1), 103-139. Google Scholar ↗
- [7] Coccorese, P., & Ferri, G. (2020). Are mergers among cooperative banks worth a dime? Evidence on efficiency effects of M&As in Italy. *Economic Modelling*, 84(1), 147-164. Google Scholar ↗
- [8] Aristei, D., & Gallo, M. (2019). Loan loss provisioning by Italian banks: Managerial discretion, relationship banking, functional distance and bank risk. *International Review of Economics & Finance*, 60(1), 238-256. Google Scholar ↗
- [9] Chavan, A., Kumbhar, R. D., & Mundhe, S. D. (2019). CBS Adoption by Cooperative Banks: A theoretical review. *International Journal of Management, IT and Engineering*, 7(12), 27-31. Google Scholar ↗
- [10] Sivaperumal, K. (2019). A Study on The Functioning of Co-Operative Bank and Job Satisfaction of Bharat Heavy Electricals Employees' Cooperative Bank Limited, Trichy. *Think India Journal*, 22(21), 796-809. Google Scholar ↗
- [11] Hesse, H., & Čihák, M. (2007).. Cooperative Banks and Financial Stability, IMF Working Paper 7(2),1-38. Google Scholar ↗
- [12] Gupta, J., & Jain, S. (2012). A study on Cooperative Banks in India with special reference to Lending Practices. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 2(10), 1-6. Google Scholar ↗
- [13] Ramu, N. (2008). Human resource management in cooperative banks in India: issues and challenges. *CAB Calling*, 32(3), 67-72. Google Scholar ↗
- [14] Nethala, V. J., Pathan, M. F. I., & Sekhar, M. S. C. (2022). A Study on Cooperative Banks in India with Special Reference to Marketing Strategies. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Business and Government*, 28(4),1-10. Google Scholar ↗
- [15] Haralayya, B. (2021). Analysis of Non-Performing Asset on Urban Cooperative Bank in India. *Iconic Research and Engineering Journals*, 5(1), 111-121. Google Scholar ↗

- [16] Matkar, A. (2012). Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for standard of customer services in Maharashtra state cooperative bank. *IUP Journal of Bank Management*, 11(3), 89-95. Google Scholar ↗
- [17] Zaman, A. U., Zaman, M. S., & Khan, N. A. (2022). Analysing the Technical Efficiency of Rural Cooperative Banks in India. *Asian Economics Letters*, 3(4), 1-6 Google Scholar ↗
- [18] Babu, K. V. S. N. J. (2012). Performance evaluation of urban co-operative banks in India. *IOSR Journal of Business and Management*, 1(5), 28-30. Google Scholar ↗
- [19] Reddy, K. N., & Chandraiah, M. (2019). Progress of Cooperative Banks in India. *International Journal of Engineering and Management Research*, 9(1), 1-4. Google Scholar ↗
- [20] Kamesam, V. (2002). Cooperative Banks in India: Strengthening through corporate governance. *RBI Bulletin*, 56(8), 551-557. Google Scholar ↗
- [21] Chandanshive, D. S. B. (2017) Performance evaluation of Co-operative banks in India. *International Journal of Advance and Innovative Research*, 6(1), 390-395. Google Scholar ↗
- [22] Khan, H. F. (2014). Current scenario and future prospects of urban cooperative banks in India. *International journal of trends in commerce and economics*, 1(3), 15-19. Google Scholar ↗
- [23] Dhirubhai, A. (2013). Challenges of core banking in co operative banking in India. *Journal of Asian Research Consortium*.3(5), 1-7. Google Scholar ↗
- [24] Karthikeyan, K. (2021). A Study on Financial Statement Analysis of Primary Agricultural Cooperative Credit Society in Paiyanoor Branch at Chengalpattu District. *ComFin Research*, 9(3), 37-43. Google Scholar ↗
- [25] Minetti, R., Murro, P., & Peruzzi, V. (2021). Not all banks are equal: Cooperative banking and income inequality. *Economic Inquiry*, 59(1), 420-440. Google Scholar ↗
- [26] Etareri, L.(2021). A Critical Analysis on Strategic Management. *International Journal of Research in Humanities and Social Studies*,8(1), 26-35. Google Scholar ↗
- [27] Aithal, P. S. (2021). Analysis of Systems & Technology Using ABCD Framework. *Srinivas Publication, India*, 8(1), 345-385. Google Scholar ↗
- [28] Capobianco, N., Basile, V., Loia, F., & Vona, R. (2021). Toward a sustainable decommissioning of offshore platforms in the oil and gas industry: a PESTLE analysis. *Sustainability*, 13(11), 1-20. Google Scholar ↗
- [29] Wang, H., Yang, X., Xu, X., & Fei, L. (2021). Exploring Opportunities and Challenges of Solar PV Power under Carbon Peak Scenario in China: A PEST Analysis. *Energies*, 14(11), 1-28. Google Scholar ↗
- [30] Demirtas, O., Derindag, O. F., Zarali, F., Ocal, O., & Aslan, A. (2021). Which renewable energy consumption is more efficient by fuzzy EDAS method based on PESTLE dimensions? *Environmental Science and Pollution Research*, 28(27), 36274-36287. Google Scholar ↗